

IN THE PLASMA MAGNETIC FIELD. PROPERTIES OF PLASMA

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Thermal conductivity of plasma does not depend on its density. The thermal conductivity coefficient of pure hydrogen plasma was calculated due to the proportionality of the thermal conductivity with the electron concentration and the length of the free path. In plasma, pressure is defined as the flow of momentum (momentum) across a cross-section of critical area. To describe the behavior of plasma in a magnetic field, let's consider the movement of a charged particle in such a field. When viewed along the line of magnetic force, a negatively charged particle moves in a clockwise direction, and a positively charged particle moves in a counterclockwise direction. The instantaneous center of the circular trajectory is called the center of rotation or the center of rotation. Since the Lorentz force is always perpendicular to the velocity vector, the magnetic field does no work on the particle.

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Any plasma in a large volume must be neutral with great accuracy, otherwise strong electrostatic forces will arise as a result of the interaction of charged particles of different signs. The properties of the plasma are determined by the sum of its components. The density of the plasma is equal to the sum of the densities of its components.

$$\rho = \rho_i + \rho_e + \rho_n = n_i m_i + n_e m_e + n_n m_n \quad (1.1)$$

where i, e, n subscripts correspond to ions, electrons, and neutral particles. If C_0 - the speed of the entire volume of the gas C_{es} - s is the speed of the electron, the individual (random) speed

$$v_{es} = C_{es} - C_0 \quad (1.2)$$

The average value of the individual velocities should probably be zero. The kinetic temperature of any component $\bar{v}e^2$ is determined by the root-mean-square velocity:

$$\frac{3}{2} \cdot kTe = \frac{1}{2} me \bar{v} e^2 \quad (1.3)$$

Here $\bar{v}e^2$ is the root mean square value of the random velocities of all particles from a given component. The average velocities of particles belonging to different components are different due to electromagnetic and similar forces, but collisions between particles reduce this difference to zero and create a state of equilibrium. In equilibrium, the average energy of thermal motion of any type of particle is the same.

Therefore, in the case of equilibrium, the indices indicating the type of particle are discarded. In the case of equilibrium, the distribution of particles according to their velocities $f(v)$ is described by Maxwell's distribution function. That is, $1sm^3$ the number of particles in the range of velocities $v, v + dv$

$$Nf(v)dv = 4\pi N \left(\frac{m}{2\pi kT} \right)^{3/2} v^2 \bar{e} \frac{mv^2}{2kT} dv, \quad (1.4)$$

where $N - 1sm^3$ is the number of particles in. Such distribution formulas are true for all types of particles. Any deviations in this distribution are eliminated by collisions. $f(v)$ the most probable speed corresponding to the maximum of the function

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2kT}{m}} \quad (1.5)$$

Since there are few collisions in the case of very high plasma, it is necessary to look separately at the summations of the individual velocity vector along the directions. Such a situation occurs in interplanetary space. The particles, roughly speaking, either fly away from the Sun, or change directions as they move perpendicular to the lines of force in the magnetic field. [1, 2]

In plasma, pressure is defined as the flow of momentum (momentum) across a cross-section of critical area. Therefore, the pressure in any direction is equal to the average momentum moving along the three coordinate directions and transported through that section. In other words, we are looking at a P tensor such that each element represents the momentum carried by all types of particles.

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} nmv\bar{x}^2 & nmv\bar{x}\bar{y} & nmv\bar{x}\bar{z} \\ nmv\bar{y}\bar{x} & nmv\bar{y}^2 & nmv\bar{y}\bar{z} \\ nmv\bar{x}\bar{z} & nmv\bar{z}\bar{y} & nmv\bar{z}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.6)$$

The non-diagonal elements of this tensor are zero (since their average values are zero due to the same velocities of the particles in the positive and negative directions). So only the diagonal elements remain.

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} nm\bar{v}x^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & nm\bar{v}y^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & nm\bar{v}z^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.6)$$

If collisions occur frequently enough, then these three diagonal elements are equal to each other and i for any direction

$$P_i = \frac{1}{3} nm\bar{v}^2 \quad (1.7)$$

is taken.

If the rarefied plasma is in a magnetic field, then the pressure in the direction of the field and in the direction perpendicular to it can be different. In this case the pressure tensor

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} P_{//} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & P_{\perp} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & P_{\perp} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} nm\bar{v}_{//}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & nm\bar{v}_{\perp}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & nm\bar{v}_{\perp}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.8)$$

is in the form of If the magnetic field is directed along the axis, $v_{//}$ and $v_{\perp}$ show the longitudinal and forward components of the velocity vector, respectively. When studying interplanetary plasma, it is necessary to take into account the difference between $P_{\perp}$ and $P_{//}$. [3, 4]

The settling time of equilibrium in plasma is called relaxation time. It is a quantity that characterizes this period t_D , during which any particle 90° changes its direction of motion. If we denote by an index any averaging property of the field (for example, concentration, average velocity, temperature), f

$$t_D = \frac{v^3}{A_D \left[\Phi \left(\frac{v}{v_f} \right) - G \left(\frac{v}{v_f} \right) \right]}, \quad (1.9)$$

$$\text{Here } A_D = \frac{8\pi e^4 n_f Z^2 Z_f^2 \ell n \Lambda}{m^2}$$

$$\Lambda = \frac{3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{1}{Z \cdot Z_f} \left(\frac{T}{157000^0} \right)^{3/2} \left(\frac{10^{24}}{0,147n_f} \right)^{1/2} \quad (1.10)$$

Z -the total charge of the particle, $T/157000^0$ -the temperature in the atomic unit, $\alpha^3 n_f$ -the number of electrons in the cube with a Bohr orbit (a), G and Φ -the parameters calculated according to the Sipsiter table. χ Suppose we want to know the relaxation rate of fast electrons in the solar corona due to elastic collisions (i.e. collisions in which the internal energy does not change). The speed of these electrons will slow down due to the collision between them, because, according to the laws of classical mechanics, energy is easily transferred between those of similar mass, and the difference in mass is extremely bad. If the energy of fast electrons $16000eV, T_f = 2 \cdot 10^6$ If $\frac{v}{v_f} \approx 10$

$^0 K$ is . Concentration $n_e = 10^9$, $\ell_n \Lambda = 40, v_1 \approx 40$. Meanwhile, electrons 25 sec. they will "cool down"

due to elastic collisions. Radiation and other effects reduce this time further.

The thermal conductivity of the plasma is proportional to the concentration of electrons and the length of the free path. Since the length of the free path is inversely proportional to the concentration, the heat conduction of the plasma does not depend on the density. Thermal conductivity of pure hydrogen plasma

$$K = 1,05 \cdot 10^{12} \frac{T^{3/2} \text{ kal}}{Z \ell_n \Lambda \text{ san}} \cdot \text{diameter cm} \quad (1.13)$$

In a strong magnetic field, the thermal conductivity of the plasma in the direction perpendicular to the lines of force decreases at a high rate; heat is carried only by ions and heat conduction

$$K_{\perp} = 3,54 \cdot 10^{25} \frac{A_i^{1/2} Z n_i^2 \ell n \Lambda \text{ kal}}{T^{1/2} B^2 \text{ san}} \text{diameter cm} \quad (1.14)$$

happens. To describe the behavior of plasma in a magnetic field, let's look at the movement of a charged particle in such a field:

Characterizing the magnetic field $\vec{B}$ - the induction vector can change in space both in value and direction. Therefore, it is convenient to show the area with lines of force. Lines of force are parallel to their vector at each point $\vec{B}$, their density is proportional to the modulus of this vector. If the magnetic field changes due to the movement of the plasma, the magnetic field lines are deformed (densified or rarefied). Before moving on to the overall motion of charged particles, let's look at the motion of an individual particle. The force acting on a particle with $\vec{B}$ charge e and mass in a magnetic field is the Lorentz force. m

$$\vec{F} = \frac{d\vec{p}}{dt} = \frac{e}{c} \vec{v} \times \vec{B}, \quad (1.15)$$

where $\vec{p}$ - is the particle's momentum (momentum) vector, $\vec{v}$ - is its velocity. The vector product on the right shows that the net force $\vec{v}$ is perpendicular to both and $\vec{B}$

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$$\rho = \frac{|P_{\perp}|c}{|e|B}, \quad (1.16)$$

where $\rho_{\perp}$ - is the component of the momentum vector perpendicular to the magnetic field.

Circular frequency of rotation

$$\omega = \frac{|e|B}{\gamma mc}, \quad (1.17)$$

$$\text{here } \gamma = \frac{P}{mv} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} = \sqrt{1 + \frac{P^2}{m^2 c^2}} \quad (1.18)$$

or relativistic correction.

$$B \cdot \rho = \frac{P_{\perp} c}{|e|} \quad (1.19)$$

The result is called magnetic stiffness and plays an important role in studying the trajectory of cosmic rays. The leading hub concept was introduced by Alven. The particle rotates around this point and at the same time moves along the trajectory determined by the non-magnetic forces. For example, an electric field parallel to a magnetic field $e\vec{E}$ interacts with the electron - force, $-\frac{e\vec{E}}{m}$ giving it momentum towards the leading center.

When a particle r moves in a spiral over the surface of a cylinder with a radius, the leading center slides into the lines of force. [5]

An electric field perpendicular to the magnetic field creates a drift perpendicular to the leading center $\vec{E}$ and $\vec{B}$ its vectors. The speed of this drift

$$v_{ap} = \frac{E_{\perp}}{B} = \frac{10^8 E_{\perp}}{B} \text{ (V / sm)} \quad (1.20)$$

If the magnetic field is uneven, then the radius of curvature of the trajectory changes with the change of field intensity. Therefore, the trajectory alternately consists of half-loops of increasing and decreasing length (long where the field is weak, short where the field is strong). As a result, in the direction perpendicular to the particle $\vec{B}$ and grad vectors $|\vec{B}|$

$$vg = \frac{v_1 \rho \text{grad}_1 B}{2B} \quad (1.21)$$

moving at drift speed.

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